

IN VITRO EVALUATION OF NEW GENERATION FUNGICIDES AGAINST RUST DISEASE OF FIG [*Cerotelium fici* (Cast.)

Arth.]

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Abstract

Fig (Ficus carica) is a dryland horticulture crop with significant export potential and good economic rewards. Rust caused by *Cerotelium fici* (Cast.) Arth. is one of the major fig disease that cause significant losses in the fig crop. The *in vitro* studies regarding efficacy of fungicides against *Cerotelium fici* (Cast.) Arth revealed that the new generation combi-fungicides were found most effective than sole fungicides. Tebuconazole 50% + Trifloxystrobin 25% WG was found to be the most effective fungicide over all fungicides showing 1.45 per cent uredospore germination count with highest inhibition percentage (97.90 %).

Key words: Fig, Rust, *Cerotelium fici*, Tebuconazole 50% + Trifloxystrobin 25% WG

Introduction

Fig (*Ficus carica* L.) is an important deciduous fruit crop grown in tropical and subtropical countries including India. It comes under Moraceae family. Edible fig is known for its fruits, is being cultivated for thousands of years. The name *Carica* comes from its origin place Carica in Asia Minor i.e. Mediterranean region (Starr *et al.*, 2003). Among biotic and abiotic factors responsible for reduction in yield, diseases caused by various pathogens are one of the major factor. Fig crop is infected by a number of diseases brought on by bacteria, viruses, and fungus. Fig rust (*Cerotelium fici*), anthracnose (*Colletotrichum gloeosporioides*), *Armillaria* rot (*Armillaria mellea*), bacterial canker (*Pseudomonas fici*), blight disease (*Ceratocystis fimbriata*), leaf spots (*Cylindrocladium scoparium* and *Cercospora fici*), aerial web blight (*Rhizoctonia solani*), fruit rot (*Phytophthora palmivora*), fig mosaic (fig mosaic virus), etc. are the common diseases observed on fig (Bose and Mitra, 2002). Among them fig rust caused by *Cerotelium fici* (Cast.) Arth. is one of the most serious disease.

Chemical and biological control based on timely disease forecasting system has been found to be successful and economical plant protection method adopted in various countries. Before recommending any fungicide, it is very essential to test its efficacy and dosage. With these views, the experiments under *in-vitro* conditions were under

$$I = \frac{C - T}{C} \times 100$$

Where,

I = Inhibition per centage

C = Spore germination under control and

T = Spore germination under respective treatment

taken to find out efficacy of various fungicides in controlling rust (*C. fici*) of fig crop.

Materials and methods

The trial on efficacy of fungicides was conducted under *in-vitro* condition at Plant Pathology laboratory at College of Agriculture, Pune, Dist. – Pune in Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with 3 replication and 9 treatments. The efficacy of four solo fungicides and four combi-fungicides were tested *in vitro* against *C. fici* by assessing percentage inhibition of spore germination. Fungicide solutions were prepared by dissolving required quantity of fungicide products in tap water. Each concentration of a fungicide was replicated three times. Single drop of uredospore suspension was added to the walls of series of cleaned cavity slides to which single drop of different fungicides were also added to get the required concentrations. Later cover slips were placed on the cavity slides. A control treatment was maintained with a drop of water. These cavity slides were kept in the petridishes lined with moist blotting paper and were incubated at room temperature. After 24 hours observations were taken in ten microscopic fields for each slide and the total number of spores germinated in each microscopic field was recorded. The average count of three cavity slides (three replications) was found out and the per cent inhibition of spore germination was calculated with the formula given by Vincent (1947) for each of fungicides.

Trade name	Common name	Chemical name	Source
Bavistin	Carbendazim 50 % WP	Methyl-2 - Benzimidazole carbamate	BASF India Ltd, Mumbai
Kavach	Chlorothalonil 75% WP	2,4,5,6 Tetrachloroisophthalo nitrite	Syngenta India Ltd
Contaf	Hexaconazole 5% EC	2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-1-(1,2,4-triazol-1-yl)hexan-2-ol	Rallis India Ltd., Mumbai
Folicure	Tebuconazole 25.9% EC	1-(4-chlorophenyl)-4,4-dimethyl-3-(1,2,4-triazol-1-ylmethyl)pentan-3-ol	Bayer Crop Science, SAS, France
Nativo	Tebuconazole 50% + Trifloxystrobin 25% WG	Triazole class of fungicides + Strobilin class of fungicides	Bayer Crop Science, SAS, France
Amistar Top	Azoxystrobin 18.2% + Difenconazole 11.4% w/w SC	Triazole class of fungicides + Strobilin class of fungicides	Syngenta India Ltd
Adama Custodia	Azoxystrobin 11% + Tebuconazole 18.3% w/w SC	Triazole class of fungicides + Strobilin class of fungicides	ADAMA Agricultural Solutions UK Ltd.

Results and discussion

All the evaluated fungicides showed considerable inhibition of spores of rust (Table No 1). Among all fungicides, the combi-product treatment of Tebuconazole 50% + Trifloxystrobin 25% WG were superior over all showing 1.45 per cent uredospore germination with highest inhibition (97.90 %). However, it was at par with Azoxystrobin 11% + Tebuconazole 18.3% w/w SC and Azoxystrobin 18.2% + Difenconazole 11.4% w/w SC with uredospore germination of 1.63 per

cent and 1.78 per cent and inhibition of 97.65 per cent and 97.43 per cent respectively. The untreated control showed the highest uredospore germination count (69.03 %).

Similar results were obtained by Sreekantappa and Naik (2004) who reported non-systemic mancozeb (0.15%) and systemic fungicide hexaconazole (0.025%) inhibited spore germination of *C. fici* to the maximum extend up to 77.4 and 91.30 per cent, respectively under laboratory condition. Poojashree *et al.*, (2021) reported that out of

fourteen fungicides evaluated, a combi-product of novel fungicide molecules, Ametoctradin 27 % + Dimethomorph 20.27 % SC at 0.1 % was found highly effective and showed the least spore germination (0.62 %). which were also in agreement with the present studies

Table 1: Germination of *C. fici* urediospores as influenced by different fungicides at 1/10th concentration *in vitro*.

Sr.No.	Treatment	Conc (%)	Germination Count (%)	Inhibition (%)
1	Carbendazim 50 % WP	0.010	5.65 (13.72)	91.82
2	Chlorothalonil 75% WP	0.200	6.30 (14.52)	90.87
3	Hexaconazole 5% EC	0.010	3.15 (10.19)	95.44
4	Tebuconazole 25.9% EC	0.010	2.63 (9.27)	96.20
5	Tebuconazole 50% + Trifloxystrobin 25% WG	0.006	1.45 (6.86)	97.90
6	Azoxystrobin 18.2% + Difenconazole 11.4% w/w SC	0.010	1.78 (7.64)	97.43
7	Azoxystrobin 11% + Tebuconazole 18.3% w/w SC	0.015	1.63 (7.28)	97.65
8	Carbendazim 50 % WP + Chlorothalonil 75% WP	0.010 and 0.020	3.48 (10.71)	94.97
9	Control	--	69.03 (56.19)	--
			SE(m) ⁺	0.68
			C.D. (5%)	2.04
			C.V.(%)	4.78

Conclusion

The *in vitro* studies regarding efficacy of fungicides against *C. fici* revealed that the new generation combi-fungicides were found most effective than sole fungicides. Tebuconazole 50% + Trifloxystrobin 25% WG was found most effective fungicide as it showed lowest spore germination and highest percentage inhibition of spores followed by Azoxystrobin 11% + Tebuconazole 18.3% w/w SC

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